

A COMPACT DESIGN EIGHT ELEMENT MULTIPLE INPUT MULTIPLE OUTPUT MILLIMETER-WAVE ANTENNA

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Abstract

In this paper, a compact design eight element multiple input multiple output millimeter-wave antenna is proposed. This proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna consists of eight antipodal Vivaldi antennas. The operating band of this proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna covers a 20-40 GHz which is intended for millimeter band 28 and 38 GHz of 5G mobile communication application. The overall dimension of the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna is $200 \times 100 \times 21.2$ mm³ and each antenna element has a size of $25 \times 8 \times 0.8$ mm³. The result shows that the return loss of the individual antenna element ($S_{11}, S_{22}, \dots, S_{88}$) at 28 and 38 GHz frequencies are -13.986 and -18.938 dB. The mutual coupling ($S_{21}, S_{31}, \dots, S_{68}, S_{78}$) of the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna are valued in the range of -30.629 to -81.429 dB, it means that the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna has a high isolation (> 14 dB) between antenna elements. The impedance bandwidth (return loss < -10 dB) is achieved in the range of the entire of the operating band (20-40 GHz). It has a good VSWR which are 1.5 and 1.2 for 28 and 38 GHz frequencies, respectively. The proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna has also shown a good envelope correlation coefficient (ECC) which is less than 0.3 (requirement). Particularly, the ECC values are correspondingly 0.00002173 at 28 GHz and 0.00000751 at 38 GHz. In addition, the obtained diversity gains are 9.96 dB at 28 GHz and 9.99 dB at 38 GHz. The proposed compact eight element MIMO mm-wave antenna has good characteristics.

Keywords: Diversity gain, ECC, Millimeter-wave, MIMO, VSWR.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the demand for high data rate in mobile communication increases exponentially. Mobile communication technology is moving forward into the fifth generation (5G). 5G can provide peak data rate 20 Gbps, maximum latency 1 ms, energy efficiency, connection density (1 million connected devices/km²), maximum mobility 500 km/h, high availability and peak spectral efficiency 30 bit/s/Hz which are detail pictured in Fig. 1 [1, 2].

Fig. 1. 5G capabilities [2].

ITU-R IMT-2020 defined 5G spectrum band into three ranges which are below 2 GHz (low frequencies i.e. 700, 800, 900, 1800 and 2100 MHz), 2-6 GHz (medium frequencies, i.e., 3.3-8 GHz, 3.8-4.2 GHz, 4.8-4.99 GHz) and above 6 GHz (high frequencies i.e. 24.25-27.5 GHz, 31.8-33.4 GHz, 37-43.5 GHz, 45.5- 0.2 GHz, 50.4-52.6 GHz, 66-76 GHz and 81-86 GHz) [3]. Low frequencies (below 2 GHz) support for the widespread area including dense urban, urban, suburban, rural. Medium frequencies (2-6 GHz) provide a good combination of capacity and coverage. High frequencies (above 6 GHz) offer an ultrahigh speed data rate. On the other side, 5G requires at least 100 MHz bandwidth at medium frequencies (2-6 GHz) and 600 MHz bandwidth at high frequencies (above 6 GHz) [3, 4]. The high frequencies around 38 and 28 GHz are favorable bands for 5G. However, by their nature that the higher frequency (mm-wave) causes an increased propagation loss due to the reduced wavelength (λ). Antenna system plays a key role in 5G capabilities. Those high data rates and wider bandwidth in 5G could be facilitated by mm-wave MIMO antenna system [5]. MIMO is a fundamental antenna system for 5G. Above 6 GHz, these mm-meter spectrum bands provide a wider bandwidth for MIMO antenna while it has some propagation challenges.

The mm-wave technology allows the development of a compact antenna, which significantly reduces the antenna's size. There are several performance challenges in the mm-wave MIMO antenna design such as mutual coupling, higher gain, wider bandwidth, and high radiation efficiency. MIMO antenna has a significant challenge to maintenance multiple numbers of the antenna within a small and compact space due to the mutual coupling appeared between two or more antenna elements of the MIMO antenna. Therefore, the development of MIMO mm-wave antenna with high performance for ultra-high data rate mobile communication application is a great interest for many researchers. MIMO mm-wave antenna has an advantage in term of spatial multiplexing which is improving capacity and link reliability.

Recently, many papers have reported a performance of millimeter wave MIMO antenna. In [6], 32-element modified bow tie antenna were arranged in an octagonal prism configuration with radius $d = 10 \lambda$, side height = 16.8λ , side length = 4.2λ and triple operation frequencies 28/38/48 GHz. Four elements modified rectangular patch MIMO antenna, operation frequency 33 GHz, was presented in [7]. These four antenna elements were placed in the size of $32.5 \times 26.6 \times 1.6 \text{ mm}^3$. Eight slotted-rectangular element MIMO antenna was presented in [8], these eight antenna elements were arranged in the dielectric substrate with a size of $16 \times 16 \times 1.6 \text{ mm}^3$. Unfortunately, this eight element MIMO had a poor mutual coupling performance. In [9], authors simulated the effect of the presence of a diode in a configurable antenna with operation frequency of 20-30 GHz for 5G. This paper only simulated a single element antenna with a $50 \times 20 \times 1.6 \text{ mm}^3$ of size. Consequently, the paper didn't present and analyze the mutual coupling and ECC parameter. Paper [10] presented the MIMO antenna performance with only two element antennas in dual operation frequencies 4.21-5.16 GHz and 7.84-8.63 GHz.

The current study contributes to developing a compact design of eight elements mm-wave MIMO antenna with high performance parameters. The antenna parameters are including mutual coupling/S parameter, VSWR, return loss, gain, bandwidth, and radiation pattern will be investigated. This paper is arranged in five sections. Section 1 delivers an introduction. Section 2 provides an overview of MIMO antenna system. Section 3 describes the proposed geometrical design of eight element-MIMO mm-wave antenna in range of 20-40 GHz spectrum frequencies. This work particularly focuses on 28 and 38 GHz. Results and discussion of eight element-MIMO will be presented in Section 4. Section 5 concludes this research.

2. Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) Antenna

Multiple input multiple output antenna systems use an l_r antenna elements at the receiver and an l_t antenna elements at the transmitter. The response of the wireless channel between the m^{th} receiver and the k^{th} transmitter is expressed as $h_{mk}(\tau, t)$. The formulation channel of MIMO can be explained by the $l_r \times l_t$ $H(\tau, t)$ matrix in Eq. (1) [11-13].

$$H(\tau, t) = \begin{bmatrix} h_{1,1}(\tau, t) & h_{2,1}(\tau, t) & \dots & h_{l_t,1}(\tau, t) \\ h_{1,2}(\tau, t) & h_{2,2}(\tau, t) & \dots & h_{l_t,2}(\tau, t) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ h_{1,l_r}(\tau, t) & h_{2,l_r}(\tau, t) & \dots & h_{l_t,l_r}(\tau, t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Based on Eq. (1) and Fig. 2, all elements in the matrix represent the phase and attenuation of the signal reach the receiver in delay τ . The correlation of the output signal and the input signal of the MIMO antenna can be formulated at the Eq. (2) [11, 14].

$$w(t) = H(\tau, t) * x(t) + u(t) \quad (2)$$

$x(t)$ is a $l_t \times 1$ transmitted information signals, $*$ denotes convolution operation, $w(t)$ is a $l_r \times 1$ received information signals and $u(t)$ is the additive white noise. The capacity of a MIMO channel can be formulated as below Eq. (3) [14].

$$C = \max_{\text{tr}(R_{ss}) \leq p} \log_2[\det(I + HR_{ss}H^H)] \quad (3)$$

where H^H is the transpose conjugate of the H channel matrix with H size is $l_r \times l_t$. R_{ss} is the covariance matrix, s is the transmitted information signal. However, MIMO channel also can be performed into linear transformation, converting the

multiple channels to $n = \min(l_r, l_t)$ of the SISO channel, with n is the number of multiplication of MIMO channel.

Fig. 2. MIMO channel modeling.

3. MIMO Millimeter-Wave Antenna Design System

The geometrical of the proposed eight elements MIMO millimeter-wave antenna is figured in Fig. 3 and its detailed dimensions are listed in Table 1. The proposed antenna is composed of eight Vivaldi antennas. In this research, we use an antipodal Vivaldi antenna (AVA) type.

Antipodal Vivaldi antenna, radiator patch is printed on the top side and ground plane in the bottom side of the substrate [15]. We use a FR 4 dielectric substrate with a ϵ_r (relative permittivity) of 4.4 and $\tan \delta$ (loss tangent) of 0.02. The thickness of the substrate is 0.8 mm. Antipodal Vivaldi antenna has an end-fire radiation pattern [16]. The eight element antipodal Vivaldi antennas are grouped into two block confrontly. Figure 4 illustrates the detail configuration of the single AVA. The antipodal Vivaldi antenna has an exponentially tapered opening slot. It has two tapered radiator arms. The tapered radiator arm patch in the top layer of FR 4 dielectric substrate is fed by a 50Ω feedline. The radiator arm on the bottom layer is attached with an exponentially tapered ground plane. The dimensions of the proposed AVA are listed in Table 2. The antipodal Vivaldi antenna mainly consists of three parts. The first part is a quarter of the elliptical taper. The second part is the parallel stripline. The last part is a triangular comb-shaped slits edge. This work simulated the proposed eight element MIMO mm-wave antenna in range of 20-40 GHz spectrum frequencies. The fabricated antenna is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 3. Geometrical of eight elements MIMO mm-wave antenna.

Fig. 4. Configuration of the antipodal Vivaldi antenna: (a) Top layer, and (b) Bottom layer.

Fig. 5. Fabricated antenna.

Table 1. Dimension of the proposed eight elements MIMO mm-wave antenna.

Parameter	<i>W</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>L1</i>	<i>L2</i>	<i>H</i>
Dimension (mm)	100	200	24	34.6	21.2

Table 2. Dimension of the proposed single antipodal Vivaldi antenna.

Parameter	<i>A=B</i>	<i>C=D</i>	<i>E=F</i>	<i>G</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>J=K</i>	<i>M=N</i>	<i>O</i>
Dimension (mm)	25	15	5	0.6	0.4	8	1	6.6

4. Results and Discussion

The performance of the proposed eight elements MIMO mm-wave antenna is discussed in detail in terms of simulation results. These MIMO antenna’s parameter performances are including return loss, mutual coupling, impedance bandwidth,

envelope correlation coefficient (ECC), diversity gain, and E & H field. Return loss is a measurement of how well the antenna and the transmission lines are matched. In the matched system, high return loss is desirable and lower insertion loss. The return loss is formulated $RL(dB) = 10 \log_{10}(P_i/P_r)$ with P_i is the incident power and P_r is the reflected power. The return loss is related to standing wave ratio (SWR). Increasing return loss corresponds to lower SWR. Generally, the SWR is thought of in term of the maximum and minimum ac voltages along the transmission line (VSWR). Antenna mutual coupling represents energy absorbed by one antenna's receiver when another nearby antenna is operating. Mutual coupling reduces the antenna efficiency and performance of antennas. The mutual coupling can be quantified by measuring the antenna isolation. The impedance bandwidth describes the range of frequencies a given return loss can be maintained (less than -10 dB). The two antennas would have a correlation of zero when one antenna was horizontally polarized, and the other was completely vertically polarized. Hence, ECC takes into account the antennas' radiation pattern shape, polarization, and the relative phase of the fields between the two antennas. In the other way, The ECC also can be determined by antenna isolation and it is the simplest way. The ECC value will be used in diversity gain calculation.

Figure 6 shows the simulated S parameters of the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna. Based on Fig. 6(a), the return loss (S_{11} , S_{22} , S_{33} , S_{44} , S_{55} , S_{66} , S_{77} , S_{88}) of the individual antenna element lies in the range of -12.057 dB to -22.587 dB. The obtained values of return loss at 28 GHz and 38 GHz frequencies are -13.986 dB and -18.938 dB. Figure 6(b) depicts the mutual coupling values (S_{21} , S_{31} , S_{41} , S_{51} , S_{61} , S_{71} , S_{81} , ..., S_{58} , S_{68} , S_{78}) of the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna which is in the range of -30.629 dB to -81.429 dB. Specifically, the mutual coupling values of the antenna elements at 28 GHz frequency is in the range of -36.591 dB to -61.427 dB and 38 GHz frequency is in the range of -48.428 dB to -72.568 dB. We can see in Fig. 6(b) that the mutual coupling values are categorized as a high isolation (> 14 dB). Hence, it means a low mutual coupling between the antenna elements. Furthermore, based on Fig. 3 this proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna design that the antenna elements are physically arranged separately from each other. The mutual coupling between the antenna elements in the MIMO mm-wave antenna depends on the directions of the current flowing on the antenna's surface.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. S parameters profile (a) Return loss, (b) Mutual coupling of the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna.

Fig. 7. Surface current distribution of the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna.

Envelope correlation coefficient (ECC) is the main parameter for a MIMO mm-wave antenna. The ECC defines a measure of how independent between two antenna’s radiation patterns. The envelope correlation coefficient (ρ) is the primary parameter to get the required diversity gain of the MIMO millimeter-wave antenna in Eqs. (4) and (5). The lower ρ value generates a higher diversity gain [17]. It can be calculated from the S parameters as follow [17]

$$|\rho_{ij}| = \left| \frac{|S_{ii}^* S_{ij} + S_{ji}^* S_{jj}|}{\sqrt{(1 - |S_{ii}|^2 - |S_{ji}|^2)(1 - |S_{jj}|^2 - |S_{ij}|^2)} \eta_{radi} \eta_{radj}} \right| \tag{4}$$

$$G_{diversity} = 10 \cdot \sqrt{1 - |\rho|^2} \tag{5}$$

where ρ_{ij} is the ECC between the i^{th} antenna and the j^{th} antenna, S_{ji} defines the mutual coupling between j^{th} antenna and i^{th} antenna.

The envelope correlation coefficient value would be 0 if the antenna elements are completely independent. Whereas, the ECC value would be 1 when the antenna elements are dependent. The ECC values are classified in three types : ECC < 0.3 is a good condition, 0.3 < ECC < 0.5 is a moderate condition, ECC > 0.5 is a bad condition. Based on Fig. 8, the highest obtained ECC value at 28 GHz frequency is 0.00002173 (ECC antenna 1-3) and 38 GHz frequency is 0.000000751 (ECC antenna 2-4), respectively. These achieved ECC values of the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna are less than 0.3 over the designed operating bands between ports in the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna design. It is acceptable for the MIMO mm-wave antenna system. We can see the detail ECC values at 28 GHz and 38 GHz frequencies in Table 3.

The diversity gain is obtained in terms of maximum theoretical diversity gain (10 dB) and envelope correlation coefficient using Eq. (5). The higher obtained value of the diversity gain indicates a better isolation. Based on Fig. 9, the obtained values of diversity gains at 28 GHz and 38 GHz frequencies are 9.96 dB and 9.99 dB.

Fig. 8. Envelope correlation coefficient profile.

Table 3. The ECC values of the eight element MIMO mm-wave antenna

Freq	ECC									
	ρ_{12}	ρ_{13}	ρ_{14}	ρ_{15}	ρ_{16}	ρ_{17}	ρ_{18}	ρ_{23}	ρ_{24}	ρ_{25}
28 GHz	3.26 10^{-7}	2.14 10^{-5}	1.057 10^{-6}	1.12 10^{-7}	9.02 10^{-7}	7.21 10^{-8}	1.91 10^{-7}	3.3 10^{-7}	5.5 10^{-7}	2.11 10^{-5}
38 GHz	1.61 10^{-7}	6.08 10^{-7}	4.55 10^{-7}	1.09 10^{-8}	3.16 10^{-8}	2.48 10^{-10}	4.89 10^{-8}	1.6 10^{-7}	6.44 10^{-7}	7.62 10^{-8}
	ρ_{26}	ρ_{27}	ρ_{28}	ρ_{34}	ρ_{35}	ρ_{36}	ρ_{37}	ρ_{38}	ρ_{45}	ρ_{46}
28 GHz	8.02 10^{-8}	9.2 10^{-8}	6.17 10^{-9}	6.76 10^{-8}	2.01 10^{-5}	5.5 10^{-7}	7.53 10^{-7}	2.07 10^{-5}	1.99 10^{-7}	8.85 10^{-8}
38 GHz	2.2 10^{-7}	1.32 10^{-8}	2.48 10^{-8}	3.84 10^{-10}	6.03 10^{-7}	7.63 10^{-8}	2.53 10^{-7}	5.53 10^{-7}	2.03 10^{-7}	1.3 10^{-8}
	ρ_{47}	ρ_{48}	ρ_{56}	ρ_{57}	ρ_{58}	ρ_{67}	ρ_{68}	ρ_{78}		
28 GHz	9.22 10^{-7}	1.05 10^{-6}	2.07 10^{-5}	7.46 10^{-7}	5.33 10^{-8}	5.5 10^{-7}	2.06 10^{-5}	2.81 10^{-7}		
38 GHz	2.68 10^{-8}	4.94 10^{-7}	6.45 10^{-7}	2.5 10^{-7}	9.49 10^{-10}	8.01 10^{-8}	6.08 10^{-7}	1.57 10^{-7}		

Fig. 9. Diversity gain profile.

Figure 10 shows a voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) of the antenna elements. The VSWR values of the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna at 28 GHz and 38 GHz frequencies are 1.5 and 1.25. These VSWR values also can be represented in terms of forwarded and reflected power. Based on Fig. 10, a VSWR of 1.5 has 4 % of power is reflected from the antenna and its 96 % is delivered to the antenna. VSWR 1.2, it means that is only 0.89 % of power is reflected from the antenna and 99.11 % is delivered to the antenna. The detail VSWR values of the eight antenna element are listed in Table 4.

The simulated E and H plane field patterns of the proposed eight element MIMO mm-wave antenna are depicted in Figs. 11 and 12. The far field parameters on the E and H planes can be described using E_θ , E_ϕ , and H_θ , H_ϕ components.

Fig. 10. VSWR profile.

Table 4. VSWR values at 28 GHz and 38 GHz frequencies

F (GHz)	Ant 1	Ant 2	Ant 3	Ant 4	Ant 5	Ant 6	Ant 7	Ant 8
28	1.5062	1.5045	1.5099	1.5108	1.5116	1.512	1.5074	1.5074
38	1.258	1.2546	1.2536	1.2565	1.2573	1.255	1.2565	1.2583

(a)

(b)

Fig. 11. Simulated E_ϕ and H_ϕ of the proposed eight element MIMO mm-wave antenna , (a) $E_{\phi=0}$ (28 GHz), (b) $E_{\phi=0}$ (38 GHz), (c) $H_{\phi=0}$ (28 GHz), (d) $H_{\phi=0}$ (38 GHz).

Fig. 12. Simulated E_θ and H_θ of the proposed 8 element MIMO mm-wave antenna (a) $E_{\theta=90}$ (28 GHz), (b) $E_{\theta=90}$ (38 GHz), (c) $H_{\theta=90}$ (28 GHz), (d) $H_{\theta=90}$ (38 GHz).

5. Conclusions

The compact eight element MIMO mm-wave antenna design is proposed. The proposed MIMO antenna is composed of eight antipodal Vivaldi antennas, which its operating band covers a 20-40 GHz. This proposed antenna is used for millimeter band 28 GHz and 38 GHz of the 5G mobile communication application. This antenna is providing a low return loss 1.5 and 1.2 at resonant frequencies 28 GHz and 38 GHz and an impedance bandwidth that is lied on the entire of the operating band (return loss < -10 dB). Low mutual coupling / high isolation (> 14 dB) and low ECC (< 0.3) between the antenna elements are achieved. In addition, the obtained diversity gains are 9.96 dB and 9.99 dB for resonant frequencies 28 GHz and 38 GHz. With these favorable characteristics, the proposed MIMO mm-wave antenna is suitable for the 5G mobile communication application. In future, we have to explore the MIMO antenna that operates in 60 GHz millimeter wave for a wider bandwidth.

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Nomenclatures

C	MIMO channel capacity
E	Electric field
H	Magnetic field
$H(\tau, t)$	MIMO channel matrix
l_r	Number of the receiver
l_t	Number of the transmitter
S	S parameters
$s(t)$	Input signal
$y(t)$	Output signal

Greek Symbols

δ	Loss tangent
ϵ_r	Relative permittivity
λ	Wavelength
τ	Delay
ρ	Envelope correlation coefficient

Abbreviations

5G	5 th Generation
AVA	Antipodal Vivaldi Antenna
FR 4	Flame Resistant 4
IMT 2020	International Mobile Telecommunication-2020
ITU-R	International Telecommunication Union-Radiocommunication Sector
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
mm-wave	Milimeter wave
VSWR	Voltage Standing Wave Ratio

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